

Educational Administration of Buddhist Schools under OBCP

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research was: to study 1) the conditions of educational administration of Buddhist schools under the Office of Buddhism in Chaiyaphum Province (OBSP) in Thailand; 2) the guidelines to promote the education administration of the mentioned Buddhist schools in the 21st century. This study was undertaken based on the mixed methods-research. The selected samples included 100 participants (educational administrators and teachers). Selected by purposive sampling, the target group was 12 samples. At this stage, the questionnaire (reliability value = .97) and the interview were used to collect the empirical data, later on, being analyzed by the following statistics: Percentage, Mean, S.D., t-test, and f-test (One Way ANOVA). The obtained qualitative data were studied by the descriptive analysis. The research findings indicate that: 1) the overall mean of samples' attitudes on conditions of educational administration of Buddhist schools under OBCP was at a high level. The highest mean was seen in 'Academic Administration,' followed by that of 'General Affairs,' 'Personnel' and 'Finance.' 2) For the aforesaid guidelines, the pedagogical curriculum of the schools should be up-to-date and adjusted in accordance with learners' needs; technology, more advanced media, and instructional innovations should be taken to improve the school evaluation systems, to develop the learning resources.

Keywords

Buddhist schools; the 21st Century; Educational Administration; Learning Management

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Introduction

Education is a fundamental right of all Thais, including monks and novices, that the government must provide in order to develop Thais of all ages to prosper in all aspects as a crucial intellectual cost for the development of skills, characteristics, and competencies in livelihoods so that they can live happily with others in society and this leads to stability of the society and the nation. Education, therefore, must be developed to be progressively equal to other countries on the world stage in the midst of the rapidly changing world of the 21st century[1].

According to the National Education Plan 2017-2036 of Thailand, there are four objectives in providing education: 1) to develop a quality and efficient education management system and process; 2) to develop Thai people to become good citizens with qualifications, skills, and competencies in line with the provisions of the Constitution of the Kingdom of Thailand, National Education Act, and National Strategy; 3) to develop Thai society as a society of learning and morality, ethics, knowledge, love, and unity in joining forces towards sustainable development of the country per the philosophy of sufficiency economy; 4) to overcome the trap of middle-income countries and to lower inequality within the country[1].

The idea to create equality of education for all Thais is not new in this country. As in the past, to promote education among the Buddhist monks, Buddhist Schools or Phrapariyattidhamma Schools were established by both Sangha Universities: Mahachulalongkornrajavidyalaya University (MCU) and Mahamakut Buddhist University. It has operated since 1889 and 1946[2]. Phrapariyattidhamma Schools under the Department of General Education refers to the schools established in the temple or in or the land of the Buddhist Foundation to educate monks and novices

according to the curriculum of the Ministry of Education. The schools can be established only with permission from the Ministry of Education and with the approval of the Sangha Education Council. The schools must provide instruction in accordance with the Ministry's curriculum. The National Buddhism Office (formerly the Department of Religion) will provide support as a subsidy according to the budget and in accordance with the criteria set by the Education Committee of Phrapariyattidhamma Schools Department of General Education [2].

Today, there are many studies focusing on the development of Phrapariyattidhamma schools in terms of educational effectiveness, development of educational indicators, trends in the 21st century [3] [4] [5] [6] [7]. However, a few studies focus on the development of Phrapariyattidhamma schools in Chaiyaphum Province. In order to make a contribution in this field of academic studies, the researchers were interested in studying the educational administration of the Buddhist schools under OBSP.

Research Objectives

This study has its aim to study 1) the conditions of educational administration of Buddhist schools under OBSP in Thailand; 2) the guidelines to promote the education administration of the mentioned Buddhist schools in the 21st century.

Research Methodology

This study was conducted by means of the mixed methods of research methodology and its population, samples and research tools are as follows:

Population and samples

The population of this research consisted of 100 school administrators and teachers in the Buddhist schools under OBCP, and the samples included 12 participants (educational administrators and teachers) under OBPC, selected by Purposive Sampling.

Research tools

In this research, two types of research tools were used to collect the data: the questionnaires and interview form:

- 1) Questionnaire about the characteristics of the respondents. It is a closed-end checklist questionnaire with the classification of the samples' position and duties, educational background, and work experience.
- 2) Likert's five rating scale questionnaire about the level of opinions towards the educational administration of Phrapariyattidhamma School under OBCP in the 21st century.
- 3) The questionnaire probing the guidelines for the administration of the schools with an open-ended style for respondents to express their personal opinions.
- 4) The interview form was used to interview the target group of 12 interviewees (6 school administrators and 6 teachers).

Research Results

Conditions of the educational administration of the Buddhist schools under OBSP:

The results of the research showed that the school administrators and teachers had their attitude on the conditions of the educational administration of the Buddhist schools in the 21st century at a high level in all aspects. The highest mean is seen in the aspect of 'Academic administration ($\bar{x} = 4.21$, S.D.= 0.47)', followed by that of 'General administration ($\bar{x} = 4.18$, S.D.= 0.54)', 'Personnel management ($\bar{x} = 4.14$, S.D.= 0.55)' and 'Budget administration ($\bar{x} = 4.13$, S.D.= 0.55)', the least. This can be described as follows:

- 1) Academic administration: this aspect was statistically rated at a high level. When considering the individual items, it was found that all items were rated at a high level. This indicates that school personnel in the Buddhist schools under OBPC were involved in planning and setting policies and various activities to promote learning in the 21st century, and they also provided opportunities for the community to participate in school activities on a regular basis. There was the installation of ethical awareness of the personnel to realize the harmful effects of anti-corruption.
- 2) Budget management: overall, this aspect was rated at a high level as same as all of its studied items: approval of procurement, budget expenditures have done according to the annual plan, which could be examined and was transparent at all levels; transparency and exactitude of planning of supplies, equipment, and buildings.
- 3) Personnel administration: the overall mean of personnel management was at a high level, and all studied items were statistically rated at a high level. The items included providing opportunities for personnel to participate in

setting evaluation criteria on a regular basis, transparency of personnel promotion; demonstration of clear criteria and methods for assessing personnel performance; allowing the personnel to set the classroom or building for maximum benefit.

- 4) General administration: the overall result of the general administration research in the 21st century was at a high level. All items were at a high level, including student affairs, where all parties were involved in building cooperation and developing schools in all aspects; regularly monitoring and evaluating the results of the educational development reported to the community; taking care of the premises effectively.

Guidelines for promoting the educational administration of Buddhist schools under OBSP

- 1) Academic administration in the 21st century of Buddhist schools relies on flexibility, adaptation, initiative, independent, social, and cross-cultural skills, productivity, and responsibility. There should be the development of the school curriculum to be up-to-date to meet the needs of the learners. Consistent with global changes, teaching, and learning by using technology media and modern computer innovations should be made in order to develop an effective evaluation system, to promote community learning resources and communication technology systems.
- 2) Budget management in the 21st century of Buddhist school is to create appropriate, cost-effective policies and budget plans. There is an audit, monitoring, and reporting of budget use. The administrators should use modern computer technology to correct and manage resources to increase efficiency in financial management.
- 3) In relation to the personnel administration, the administrators should create a personnel management system, the educational personnel promotion, and the development of human resource management systems by applying moral principles appropriately for the promotion of salary with morality, ethics, and performance evaluation.
- 4) For the general administration of the schools in the 21st century, the administrators should develop a modern educational and information network system for promoting collaboration with other educational institutions and management of educational institutions according to policies and plans.

Discussion

As mentioned above, the results of this study in all four major aspects are in line with the National Education Plan in terms of using modern technology (ICT) in managing the Buddhist schools in the 21st century [1]. Also, the outcomes of the study suggest that the administrators should create the 21st skills for the learners. This is confirmed with the National Education Plan about the learners' characteristics and learning skills in the 21st century called '3Rs8Cs': 3Rs (Reading, Writing and Arithmetic); 8Cs (Critical Thinking and Problem Solving, Creativity and Innovation, Cross-cultural Understanding, Collaboration, Teamwork and Leadership, Communications, Information and Media Literacy, Computing and ICT Literacy, Career and Learning Skills, Compassion) [1]. This is also consistent with the

study of Panich [8], mentioning that skills in the 21st century and subject matters are important but not sufficient for learning in the 21st century. The teacher, therefore, should pay attention to guiding and helping activities that allow each student to assess their own learning progress. Based on the interviews, the academic administration should focus on the core subjects consisting of the mother tongue language and the world's major languages, mathematics, art, governance and civics duties, economics, science, geography, and history. These core subjects lead to formulating an important conceptual and strategic framework for the management of interdisciplinary or 21st-century topics with promoting 21st-century skills as follows:

1.1) learning and innovation skills: it will determine the readiness of students into today's increasingly complex world of work, including creativity and innovation, critical thinking and problem solving, communication and collaboration;

1.2) information, media, and technology skills: since the information has been disseminated through many media and technology today, learners must therefore have the ability to demonstrate critical thinking skills and perform a variety of tasks by relying on knowledge in many areas, including information, media, and technology;

1.3) life and career skills: to successfully live and work at the present, students need to develop key life skills (self-resilience and adaptation), initiative and independence, social and cross-cultural skills, productivity, accountability, leadership, and responsibility. This is in line with the studies of Palakul [9], which reported similar results.

Recommendations

First, the relevant educational agencies should promote the importance of management in the 21st century and apply it in their organization. Second, the Office of the Phrapariyattidhamma Schools under OBCP should be manage the training for administrators and teachers to promote and develop their operational potential in educational institution management in the 21st century in accordance with the government policies and government regulations.

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